

Spring 2025 Mule Deer Survey: Gardiner Basin

Prepared by: Michael Yarnall, Livingston Area Wildlife Biologist

2025 Survey

Survey Details

Date: 9 May 2025

Pilot: Neil Cadwell (FWP)

Observers: Michael Yarnall (FWP) and Noah Starling (FWP)

Aircraft: A-star (helicopter)

Objective: Obtain a total count and classify deer as adults or fawns in the Gardiner Trend Area as an index of total numbers and population trend. The age and sex structure are characterized relative to the number of adult deer.

Flight Details: This survey was combined with bighorn sheep survey efforts. We took off from the Gardiner airport at 6:26 and surveyed mule deer in the Gardiner Basin Trend Area, beginning on the west side of the Yellowstone because the morning light hits that side of the basin earliest. We crossed the river near at the north end of the trend area and surveyed south to the vicinity of Little Trail Creek, when we returned to the airport to refuel (9:42-10:03). We continued working southward, finishing the mule deer survey near Deckard Flats at approximately 11:12. We then flew to the upper end of Tom Miner Basin to survey high elevation bighorn sheep winter range. Total flight time was 7.3 hours, including 5.1 hours of survey time and 2.2 hours of pilot ferry time.

Survey Conditions: The temperature was 45 F at takeoff and 62 F at the end of our flight. Winds were light at takeoff (5-6 mph), and remained light throughout the survey (generally <10 mph). Lighting conditions were good with primarily bright sun. Because this survey was conducted later than normal, vegetation green up was substantially more advanced than it usually is. Deer were primarily up feeding at the beginning of the survey, but warm temperatures and advanced green up contributed to deer bedding down in the shade during the latter part of the survey. Overall survey quality was good.

Survey Results

We observed **869** total mule deer in **132** groups. We classified **612** adults and **247** fawns; **10** deer were unclassified (Figure 1). This resulted in **40.4 fawns per 100 adults**. Observed recruitment was similar on both sides of the Yellowstone River (Table 1).

We also observed **2** golden eagles, **2** bald eagles, **1** black bear, and **121** bighorn sheep in addition to elk, pronghorn, and bison.

Figure 1: Flight path and locations of mule deer groups (red) and incidental observations of other species (blue) during the 2025 survey of the Gardiner Trend Area (outlined in purple).

Table 1: Mule deer distribution by herd unit as observed during the 2025 spring survey of the Gardiner Trend Area.

Subunit	Adults	Fawn	Unclassified	Total Deer
Slip and Slide Creek to Little Trail Creek	158	59	0	217
Little Trail Creek to Deckard Flats	224	89	10	323
West of Yellowstone River	187	78	0	265
Yellowstone National Park	43	21	0	64
Total	612	247	10	869

Population Trends

This year's total count (**869**) was a 16 percent decrease from the 2023 count of 1032 (Figure 2). The total count was 37 percent lower than the 10-year average (**1386**) and 53 percent lower than the long-term average of counts since 1986 (**1832**, **SE = 73.4**, Figure 2). However, the proportion of deer observed that were fawns was notably higher this year (Figure 3, Figure 4); the observed number of fawns per 100 adults (**40.4**) was 103 percent higher than the 2023 ratio of 19.9 and is 2 percent above the long-term average (**39.7**, **SE = 2.1**). Montana's Adaptive Harvest Management (AHM) plan for mule deer designates the Gardiner Basin as part of the Southern Mountains Mule Deer Management Area, with a recruitment standard of 30-45 fawns per 100 adults. Ratios observed in the Gardiner Basin have fluctuated above and below this range; the observed ratio this spring is within the recruitment standard (Figure 4).

The harsh winter of 2022-2023 likely contributed to low fawn:adult ratios observed in spring 2023. There was a cold and snowy period last winter (primarily mid January to mid February) which served to concentrate animals on the winter range. However, conditions prior to that were mild, and a warmer period in late February stripped some low elevation snow. On the whole, winter 2024-2025 was not extreme, which likely contributed to the good recruitment levels observed during spring 2025. It is possible that the reduced total number of deer observed during this survey was due in part to the lateness of the survey, which was caused by challenges associated with aircraft availability and maintenance. Because the survey was flown later than normal, spring green up was substantially more advanced. It is possible that some deer had already begun to move away from their winter ranges (and outside the trend area). Future surveys will provide insight into whether the low number of deer observed this year was due to the late survey or if it represents an actual population decline. It is important to note that aerial surveys are subject to both population and sampling variability. Annual results should be interpreted with caution; inferences based on long term trends are more robust.

Figure 2: Total mule deer numbers observed during spring surveys of the Gardiner Trend Area located in HD 313, 1986-Present. Note that the 10-year and 20-year averages are the average of all surveys spanning 10/20 years up to and including the current year; because surveys are usually conducted every year, this average typically includes about 10/20 surveys, but may include fewer during decades where an annual survey was not conducted. The long-term average includes all data through the current year.

Figure 3: Number of total mule deer, adults, and fawns observed during spring surveys of the Gardiner Trend Area located in HD 313, 1990-Present.

Figure 4: Fawn:Adult ratios observed during spring surveys of the Gardiner Trend Area located in HD 313, 1987-Present. The grey ribbon indicates the recruitment standard of 30-45 fawns per 100 adults for southern mountain areas identified by Montana’s Adaptive Harvest Management Plan for mule deer. Note that the 10-year and 20-year averages are the average of all surveys spanning 10/20 years up to and including the current year; because surveys are usually conducted every year, this average typically includes about 10/20 surveys, but may include fewer during decades where an annual survey was not conducted. The long-term average includes all data through the current year.

Harvest and Management History

The Gardiner trend area informs management in HD 313 and HD 314 where it is located. Additionally, the data from the Gardiner trend area also contributes to management of mule deer in HDs 316 and 317. HDs 313, 314, 316, and 317 are within the Southern Mountains Population Management Unit (as described in FWP's 2021 Mule Deer Adaptive Harvest Management plan).

Each hunting district is discussed separately below.

HD 313 Harvest

HD 313 is a mule deer special management district. Mule deer wintering in the Gardiner Basin are primarily migratory, some traveling long distances from many different summer ranges. Once deer arrive on winter range in the Gardiner Basin they are highly vulnerable to harvest due to the open terrain, large amounts of public land, and road systems that facilitate hunter access in areas of high mule deer use. A special management season has been in place since 1994 which allows a three week buck season and no buck harvest opportunity during the final two weeks of the general season. These changes were made in fall 1994 following three years of a "2-Point Mule Deer Season" during 1991-1993 which did not achieve objectives. These changes were made with the objectives of improving quantity and quality of bucks, specifically to:

- Maintain a post season ratio of at least 15 bucks:100 does (previously 4-6 bucks/100 does)
- Increase the percentage of older bucks (≥ 2.5 years) in the post season population to 35% or more (previously 25-29%).

The buck:doe ratio observed during the post-2024 hunting season survey was very slightly above the minimum goal and the objectives of the 3-week buck season have been met most years since it was established (See Post-2024 Hunting Season Mule Deer Survey report for additional details). Antlerless harvest has been permitted with antlerless B licenses in varying numbers over the years (Table 2).

In December 2023, the Fish and Wildlife Commission adopted a change to the boundary for HD 313, which impacted mule deer opportunity in 2024. The HD 313/314 boundary was adjusted to move the portion of HD 313 west of the Yellowstone River into HD 314. Beginning in 2024, this area between Sphinx Creek and Yellowstone National Park is now managed under the regulations for HD 314, including a 5-week season for buck mule deer. This change prevents direct comparisons of to prior harvest levels because the it is impossible to separate harvest that occurs in the southern end of new HD 314 (old HD 313 west of the Yellowstone) from harvest that occurs in the remainder of HD 314. In figures shown below, the dashed vertical line at 2024, indicates that data from 2024 and later is **not** directly comparable to data from prior years.

Total harvest has trended down in recent years, though harvest increased notably in 2024 (Figure 5); this decline was driven by a decline in buck harvest, as antlerless harvest has been relatively stable (Figure 6) since 2018. The increase in 2024 is particularly notable in light of the boundary change described above, because the increased harvest occurred in a smaller area. The 2022 hunting season saw a moderate increase in mule deer harvest (Figure 5), but a decline was observed in 2023. The 2022 increase was likely caused in part by earlier winter conditions, which moved more deer into the Gardiner Basin before the mule deer season closed. Additionally, the early winter weather stimulated elk migration, which increased hunter interest and may have increased the number of hunters on the landscape that could harvest mule deer. A mild fall in 2023 may have contributed to limited harvest during that hunting season. Although buck harvest has trended down in recent years, the proportion of larger bucks harvested (≥ 4 antler points on one side) has remained relatively stable (Table 2). Mule deer buck harvest trends are shown in Figures 7 and 8; excepting 2024, buck harvest has been below the long-term average since 2019.

Due to spring survey results indicating declining mule deer numbers (Figure 2) and declining harvest (Figures 5 and 6), antlerless opportunity was reduced for the 2012-2013 seasons. Mule deer antlerless licenses were largely eliminated statewide for the 2014-2015 seasons due to concerns over statewide mule deer numbers.

As the number of mule deer observed in the Gardiner Basin increased, antlerless B licenses were reinstated with a limited quota of 50 in 2016. This quota was increased to 100 in 2018.

When the population is within 30% of the long-term average, Montana's Adaptive Harvest Management plan for mule deer recommends none-moderate numbers of antlerless B licenses. When the population is substantially below the long term-average, the AHM plan recommends limiting antlerless harvest to B licenses issued to respond to localized game damage situations. In light of reduced deer numbers and low recruitment observed during the spring 2023 survey, a within-quota adjustment was made to lower the number of B licenses available for the 2023 hunting season. Realized antlerless harvest at the current quota level (Table 2) is low enough that the impact of antlerless harvest on population trend is likely negligible.

Hunter effort, represented by the number of hunter days and by the number of days per harvested mule deer are shown in figures 9 and 10 (hunter effort data is not collected every year). Although FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between whitetail and mule deer effort, the level of whitetail harvest in HD 313 is negligible and these figures represent mule deer hunter effort.

Figure 5: Estimated total mule deer harvest in HD 313, 2004-Present. The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each annual total harvest estimate. Note that the 10-year average is the average of all surveys spanning 10 years up to and including the current year. The long-term average includes all data through the current year (i.e. the sample size increases in later years). Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 6: Estimated total, buck, and antlerless mule deer harvest in HD 313, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 7: Estimated mule deer buck harvest in HD 313, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 8: Estimated mule deer buck harvest and long-term averages in HD 313, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 9: Estimated total deer hunter days in HD 313, 2004-Present (hunter effort estimates are not collected every year). The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each year's hunter day estimate. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. However, in HD 313 whitetail deer hunting is negligible.

Figure 10: The estimated number of hunter days per mule deer harvested in HD 313. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. However, in HD 313 whitetail deer hunting is negligible.

Table 2: Estimated harvest mule deer in HD 313, 2004-Present

License Year	Total Harvest ^a	Antlerless Harvest	B License Quota ^b	Buck Harvest	Proportion Bucks \geq 4 Points ^c	Hunter Days per Harvested Mule Deer ^d
2004	270	60	175	210	0.438	11
2005	336	87	175	248	0.598	11
2006	482	76	175	406	0.589	13
2007	299	91	175	209	0.608	14
2008	250	108	325	142	0.668	17
2009	287	85	325	202	0.640	15
2010	221	97	325	124	0.537	18
2011	230	107	325	124	0.605	18
2012	160	41	85	118	0.671	
2013	246	48	85	198	0.636	19
2014	202	0	0	202	0.706	
2015	206	0	0	206	0.611	
2016	264	21	50	243	0.601	
2017	303	25	50	278	0.587	16
2018	258	38	100	220	0.631	
2019	234	41	100	193	0.554	23
2020	174	38	100	135	0.581	
2021	164	25	100	140	0.645	28
2022	188	38	100	151	0.657	
2023	156	9	25	147	0.529	31
2024 ^e	233	9	20	225	0.560	

^a Rounding error may result in an estimated total that is different than the sum of the buck and antlerless harvest.

^b Prior to 2014, B licenses in HD 313 were issued for 3 separate subunits; this column represents the total issued in all 3 subunits.

^c The proportion of bucks harvested that had at least 4 antler points on one side.

^d The estimated total hunter days divided by the estimated total number of mule deer harvested. Note that FWP’s effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail deer hunting effort. In HD 313, the whitetail hunting is negligible.

^e Due to a boundary change by the Fish and Wildlife Commission prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years.

HD 314 Harvest

HD 314 does not have a separate trend area; management is informed in part by the Gardiner Trend Area in adjacent HD 313, as well as by evaluating trends in harvest and other observations. The Adaptive Harvest Management Plan recommends an “antlered buck” season structure for both archery and general seasons with none to moderate numbers of antlerless B licenses under a standard regulation and B licenses restricted to localized game damage situations when a restrictive season type is warranted.

Total mule deer harvest in HD 314 (Figure 11) has generably been lower than harvest observed in the early 2000s, but increased in 2024. It is possible that some of the increased harvest in 2024 was due to the boundary adjustment which increased the size of HD 314, but it’s not possible to determine how much (if any) of the increase was due specifically to the boundary adjustment. Much of the decline in total harvest (Figure 11) since the early 2000s is explained by a reduction in antlerless harvest (Figure 12) following quota reductions for antlerless B licenses. The proportion of bucks that are greater than 4 points on at least one side fluctuates annually, but in most years harvest estimates indicate that over half the bucks harvested are at least 4 points

(Figure 13, Table 3). Excepting 2024, buck harvest has been slightly below the long-term average since 2017 (Figure 14).

Mule deer B licenses were reduced in 2012. In 2014, most antlerless harvest opportunity was eliminated statewide due to concerns over statewide mule deer numbers. In 2018, 100 B licenses were reintroduced in HD 314. Realized antlerless harvest at that quota level (Table 3) is low enough that the impact of antlerless harvest on population trend is likely negligible.

Hunter effort, represented by the number of hunter days and by the number of days per harvested mule deer are shown in figures 15 and 16 (hunter effort data is not collected every year). It is important to note that FWP's deer hunting effort estimates do not differentiate between whitetail and mule deer hunting effort; the figures below represent the combined deer hunting effort in HD 314.

Figure 11: Estimated total mule deer harvest in HD 314, 2004-Present. The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each annual total harvest estimate. Note that the 10-year average is the average of all surveys spanning 10 years up to and including the current year. The long-term average includes all data through the current year (i.e. the sample size increases in later years). Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 12: Estimated total, buck, and antlerless mule deer harvest in HD 314, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 13: Estimated mule deer buck harvest in HD 314, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 14: Estimated mule deer buck harvest and long-term averages in HD 314, 2004-Present. Due to a boundary change prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years; this is indicated by the dashed vertical line.

Figure 15: Estimated total deer hunter days in HD 314, 2004-Present (hunter effort estimates are not collected every year). The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each year's hunter day estimate. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. This metric should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

Figure 16: The estimated number of hunter days per mule deer harvested in HD 314. Note that FWP’s hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. This is a very coarse metric that should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

Table 3: Estimated harvest mule deer in HD 314, 2004-Present.

License Year	Total Harvest ^a	Antlerless Harvest	B License Quota	Buck Harvest	Proportion Bucks \geq 4 Points ^b	Hunter Days per Harvested Mule Deer ^c
2004	529	104	223	424	0.599	15
2005	380	91	225	290	0.529	16
2006	448	88	223	357	0.530	17
2007	370	118	225	252	0.597	18
2008	337	101	300	235	0.564	25
2009	303	131	300	173	0.625	25
2010	288	118	300	170	0.572	26
2011	312	115	300	198	0.561	23
2012	248	27	75	220	0.625	
2013	231	46	75	185	0.542	34
2014	253	0	0	253	0.520	
2015	186	0	0	186	0.661	
2016	291	3	0	288	0.581	
2017	218	3	0	215	0.602	32
2018	244	34	101	210	0.622	
2019	231	36	100	195	0.526	30
2020	192	26	101	165	0.703	
2021	233	24	100	208	0.638	39
2022	236	13	101	223	0.485	
2023	234	23	100	212	0.546	38
2024 ^d	335	27	100	308	0.626	

^a Rounding error may result in an estimated total that is different than the sum of the buck and antlerless harvest.

^b The proportion of bucks harvested that had at least 4 antler points on one side.

^c The estimated total hunter days divided by the estimated total number of mule deer harvested. Note that FWP's effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail deer hunting effort. This is a very coarse metric that should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

^d Due to a boundary change by the Fish and Wildlife Commission prior to the 2024 hunting season, harvest data from 2024 onward is not directly comparable to prior years.

HD 317 Harvest

HD 317 does not have a separate trend area; management is informed in part by the Gardiner Trend Area in adjacent HD 313, as well as by evaluating trends in harvest and other observations. The Adaptive Harvest Management Plan recommends an “antlered buck” season structure for both archery and general seasons with none to moderate numbers of antlerless B licenses under a standard regulation and B licenses restricted to localized game damage situations when a restrictive season type is warranted.

Total mule deer harvest in HD 317 (Figure 17) has generally increased in the last decade, but has been subject to substantial annual fluctuations. Excepting limited harvest via B licenses, harvest is primarily of antler-buck mule deer (Figure 18). The proportion of bucks that are greater than 4 points on at least one side fluctuates annually, but in most years harvest estimates indicate that over half the bucks harvested are at least 4 points (Figure 19, Table 4). Excepting low harvest years in 2020 and 2024, buck harvest has been above the long-term average since 2012 (Figure 20).

Mule deer B licenses were reduced in 2012. In 2014, most antlerless harvest opportunity was eliminated

statewide due to concerns over statewide mule deer numbers. In 2018, 85 B licenses were reintroduced in HD 317. Realized antlerless harvest at that quota level (Table 4) is low enough that the impact of antlerless harvest on population trend is likely negligible.

Hunter effort, represented by the number of hunter days and by the number of days per harvested mule deer are shown in figures 21 and 22 (hunter effort data is not collected every year). It is important to note that FWP’s deer hunting effort estimates do not differentiate between whitetail and mule deer hunting effort; the figures below represent the combined deer hunting effort in HD 317.

Figure 17: Estimated total mule deer harvest in HD 317, 2004-Present. The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each annual total harvest estimate. Note that the 10-year average is the average of all surveys spanning 10 years up to and including the current year. The long-term average includes all data through the current year (i.e. the sample size increases in later years).

Figure 18: Estimated total, buck, and antlerless mule deer harvest in HD 317, 2004-Present.

Figure 19: Estimated mule deer buck harvest in HD 317, 2004-Present.

Figure 20: Estimated mule deer buck harvest and long-term averages in HD 317, 2004-Present.

Figure 21: Estimated total deer hunter days in HD 317, 2004-Present (hunter effort estimates are not collected every year). The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each year's hunter day estimate. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. This metric should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

Figure 22: The estimated number of hunter days per mule deer harvested in HD 317. Note that FWP’s hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. This is a very coarse metric that should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

Table 4: Estimated harvest mule deer in HD 317.

License Year	Total Harvest ^a	Antlerless Harvest	B License Quota	Buck Harvest	Proportion Bucks \geq 4 Points ^b	Hunter Days per Harvested Mule Deer ^c
2004	227	21	72	206	0.572	18
2005	212	48	75	164	0.444	16
2006	251	37	75	214	0.513	19
2007	202	39	75	164	0.636	24
2008	179	68	125	111	0.439	29
2009	134	41	125	92	0.696	33
2010	158	56	125	101	0.527	31
2011	178	42	125	136	0.635	30
2012	180	23	30	158	0.655	
2013	178	18	30	160	0.562	38
2014	190	0	0	190	0.522	
2015	163	3	0	160	0.659	
2016	243	5	0	238	0.602	
2017	247	3	0	244	0.506	30
2018	306	38	85	269	0.578	
2019	207	15	85	192	0.567	34
2020	195	32	85	163	0.577	
2021	217	32	85	184	0.675	36
2022	298	42	85	255	0.553	
2023	240	22	85	218	0.547	32
2024	184	29	85	155	0.631	

^a Rounding error may result in an estimated total that is different than the sum of the buck and antlerless harvest.

^b The proportion of bucks harvested that had at least 4 antler points on one side.

^c The estimated total hunter days divided by the estimated total number of mule deer harvested. Note that FWP’s effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail deer hunting effort. This is a very coarse metric that should be interpreted with caution, because changes in whitetail hunting effort could influence potential conclusions independent of any changes in mule deer hunting effort.

HD 316 Harvest

HD 316 does not have a separate trend area; management is informed in part by the Gardiner Trend Area in adjacent HD 313, as well as by evaluating trends in harvest and other observations. This hunting district is nearly all within the Absaroka-Beartooth Wilderness Area and is primarily summer-range only. HD 316 is managed to provide a special backcountry hunt opportunity. The Adaptive Harvest Management Plan specifies an early rifle season which begins 15 September and no archery-only season.

Total mule deer harvest in HD 316 (Figure 23) has fluctuated over the years. Harvest increased substantially in 2024 (Figure 23). No B-licenses are issued in this district, and any reported antlerless harvest (Figure 24) is likely the result of either accidental/illegal harvest or misreporting by hunters during FWP’s harvest survey. The proportion of bucks that are greater than 4 points on at least one side fluctuates annually, but in most years harvest estimates indicate that over half the bucks harvested are at least 4 points (Figure 25, Table 5). The proportion of harvested bucks with \geq 4 points is generally higher than other HDs within the Southern Mountains Population Management Unit. This is expected, in part because the backcountry nature of this unit means the hunters are more likely to exclusively target larger, mature animals. Excepting the high harvest in 2024, harvest had trended down slightly, but harvest levels are low enough in this district that

this trend is likely within normal sampling variation (Figure 26). Future harvest surveys will provide insight into whether 2024 was a single year aberration, or represents the start of an increasing trend in harvest.

Hunter effort, represented by the number of hunter days and by the number of days per harvested mule deer are shown in figures 27 and 28 (hunter effort data is not collected every year). Although FWP’s hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between whitetail and mule deer effort, the level of whitetail harvest in HD 316 is negligible and these figures represent mule deer hunter effort.

Figure 23: Estimated total mule deer harvest in HD 316, 2004-Present. The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each annual total harvest estimate. Note that the 10-year average is the average of all surveys spanning 10 years up to and including the current year. The long-term average includes all data through the current year (i.e. the sample size increases in later years).

Figure 24: Estimated total, buck, and antlerless mule deer harvest in HD 316, 2004-Present.

Figure 25: Estimated mule deer buck harvest in HD 316, 2004-Present.

Figure 26: Estimated mule deer buck harvest and long-term averages in HD 316, 2004-Present.

Figure 27: Estimated total deer hunter days in HD 316, 2004-Present (hunter effort estimates are not collected every year). The shaded red ribbon represents the 80 percent confidence interval for each year's hunter day estimate. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. However, in HD 316 whitetail deer hunting is negligible.

Figure 28: The estimated number of hunter days per mule deer harvested in HD 316. Note that FWP's hunter effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail hunting days. However, in HD 316 whitetail deer hunting is negligible.

Table 5: Estimated harvest mule deer in HD 316, 2004-Present.

License Year	Total Harvest^a	Antlerless Harvest	Buck Harvest	Proportion Bucks \geq 4 Points^b	Hunter Days per Harvested Mule Deer^c
2004	27	0	27	0.659	35
2005	34	0	34	0.539	12
2006	22	0	22	0.332	33
2007	30	0	30	0.631	19
2008	24	0	24	0.872	16
2009	23	0	23	0.500	36
2010	11	0	11	1.000	23
2011	6	0	6	0.509	55
2012	17	0	17	0.667	
2013	14	0	14	0.400	28
2014	17	0	17	0.503	
2015	20	0	20	0.570	
2016	21	0	21	0.570	
2017	27	3	24	0.623	24
2018	27	0	27	0.569	
2019	24	0	24	0.570	20
2021	11	0	11	0.649	56
2022	17	0	17	0.801	
2023	23	0	23	0.724	38
2024	42	3	39	0.374	

^a Rounding error may result in an estimated total that is different than the sum of the buck and antlerless harvest.

^b The proportion of bucks harvested that had at least 4 antler points on one side.

^c The estimated total hunter days divided by the estimated total number of mule deer harvested. Note that FWP's effort estimates do not differentiate between mule deer and whitetail deer hunting effort. In HD 316, the whitetail hunting is negligible.